

Evolution of the business ecosystem of innovative development in Kaluga Region

Margarita Ivanova^{1*}

Abstract

The analysis of the possibilities of using the ecosystem approach in the biological and economic sciences has been carried out, and similar principles in their creation and development have been identified. The regularities of sustainable development of business ecosystems are revealed, taking into account the provisions of the science of tectology, in particular the law of least. The key role of innovation as a response to external and internal threats to the stability of the ecosystem is determined. The evolution of the business ecosystem of Kaluga region in terms of the formation of a value chain by regional institutions is considered and directions for its further modernization and ensuring the sustainability of development are proposed.

Keywords

Ecosystem — Innovation — Value Chain

¹ *Department of National Technological Initiative, JSC 'Agency for Innovative Development - Center for Cluster Development of Kaluga Region', Obninsk, Russia*

*margaivanova@yandex.ru

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Introduction

The long-overdue desire to give humanity a natural species classification in order to consistently study the mores of people and their relationships with each other as early as the 19th century was metaphorically formulated in the preface to *The Human Comedy* by O. Balzac[1]. The metaphor put forward by him compared people with animal species, and human society with the environment¹.

¹ 'Society is like Nature. After all, the Society creates from a person, according to the environment where he acts, as many diverse species as they exist in the animal world. The difference between a soldier, a worker, an official, a lawyer, a bum, a scientist, a statesman, a merchant, a sailor, a poet, a poor man, a priest is just as significant, although more difficult to discern, as what distinguishes a wolf, a lion, a donkey, crow, shark, seal, sheep, etc. Therefore, **species in human society** exist and will always exist, as well as species of the animal kingdom.'

It is surprising that nowadays, at the next turn of the evolutionary spiral, the same, re-disguised Balzac model of the world is consistently and steadily renewed in economic forms, where, due to rivalry and external pressure of the environment, new ones come to replace the old ones, meeting the spirit of modern times. Along with new species, new units, groups and classes appear. The human kingdom, like its biological environment, constantly experiences external and internal pressure, seeking to destroy the existing organization under the onslaught of what is commonly called challenges. The new era obliges us to constantly be in search of solutions that meet modern challenges. The stability and reliability of the state and its economy depends on a timely and effective response.

World history has accumulated enough facts of building a multi-structured system of businesses, corporations and industries, as well as social institutions using effective management methods based on the latest achievements of science and technology. To analyze the changes in species diversity that characterizes the modern infrastructural evolution of society, an undoubted help is provided by the ecological, that is, the "biological view" of its economy, if only because the very concept of **ecosystem** by birth is due to one of the scientific branches of biology - ecology.

1. Comparison of biological and business ecosystem infrastructures

Ecosystem in biology is a dynamic complex of communities of plants, animals, microorganisms and their inanimate environment interacting as a functional unit [2]. The ecosystem

approach seeks to achieve and integrate three main objectives. Firstly, the conservation of species, secondly, the sustainable use of the components of biodiversity and, finally, the distribution of benefits in the [3] ecosystem.

Species Conservation involves the maintenance of ecosystems and natural habitats, and the protection and restoration of viable populations in their natural habitats.

Sustainable use refers to the qualitative and quantitative use of biological components that will not result in long-term loss of biodiversity and will preserve species biological potential to meet the needs and expectations of not only current but future generations.

Due to evolutionary changes, biological communities are provided with an original structure, given by the number and size of populations, their interaction, as well as dynamics due to quantitative changes, the composition of participants and the nature of their interaction. Natural communities consist of many different species, some of which play a decisive role in terms of the possibility of the existence and development of the community as a whole. The biological kingdom has numerous examples of the collective arrangement of ecosystem communities that go beyond one species:

- insects pollinating flower plants support and regulate not only hereditary transmission of traits, but also the process of species mutations;
- corals form the exoskeleton of reefs that protect many species of marine life from sea waves and currents;
- starfish, by inhibiting the growth of the mollusk population, adjust the ratio and biodiversity of species in the oceanic community.

The simple truth is that every element, species of community, has its own place and its own special role. Evolution is not alien to human society, in which each of its members, businesses, corporations, institutions are assigned separate competencies to perform specific functions. Startups supply business and population with modern services, latest technologies and professional staff; accelerators support start-ups, improve the quality of projects, open innovation leaders; corporations pay taxes, create jobs, and maintain social stability.

The life and existence of a biological ecosystem is possible only when nutrients and energy do not decrease, move freely, make cycles and are available to organisms in the environment (atmosphere, soil and water), so that the elements of the ecosystem are able to adapt to changeable and, as a rule, deteriorating living conditions. To characterize the structure of the above dynamics in ecology, the concept of **food chains** is used.

In the economic ecosystem, in addition to natural resources, there is a movement of production products, capital and services, which together constitutes a cycle of values created as a result of the production, organizational and innovative activities of the ecosystem participants. For the ecological characterization of the structure of the economy, the concept

of **value chains** could be quite reasonable. Within the framework of the ecological approach, it becomes quite clear that both of these chains are not only ecologically interrelated, but also closely interdependent.

2. Ecosystem balance problem

The ecosystem in its dynamic development strives to achieve a state of equilibrium, i.e. to preserve the diversity of species, even if their numbers and frequency of occurrence change. In ecology, two parameters characterize the variability of an ecosystem - resilience and elasticity [4].

The ability of an ecosystem to remain in equilibrium despite various influences reflects resilience, and elasticity is determined by the rate at which the ecosystem returns to equilibrium after its loss. The nature of the ecosystem is sometimes changed by people in their activity so much that it completely loses its elasticity, and hence the ability to return to an equilibrium, stable state.

When referring to the sustainability of ecosystems in the economy, one should certainly recall the **law of relative resistance** (the law of least), formulated at the beginning of the 20th century by the founder of universal organizational science A. Bogdanov. Its formulation boils down to the following thesis: *the total stability of the complex in relation to a given environment is, obviously, a complex result of the partial stability of different parts of this complex in relation to the influences directed at them* [5]. In other words, the structural stability of the whole is given by its least partial stability. In Russian folklore, this pattern is known in the form of a saying: *where it is thin, there it breaks*.

The general organizational law of Bogdanov refers to any kind of integral formations in nature, society, and economy. For example, if one of the links in the “startup-accelerator-corporation” chain is weakened, then the level of functionality of the entire system gradually decreases. When an accelerator does not have sufficient competencies in the selection and mentoring of startups in the program, then either the “funnel” of projects is not extensive enough, or the selected projects are devoid of strategic value. A startup managed by a low-skilled team, which lacks coordination due to undeveloped communication channels, is unlikely to be able to bring a quality product to the market and interest an investor in its development.

3. Ecosystem as an environment of species specialization

It is known that economic systems in the long term are almost always unstable, loss of stability for them is rather a rule, and economic development itself is conditioned by constantly changing cycles. One of the iconic economists who paid special attention to the problem of cyclicity in economics was K. Marx. His famous “Capital” describes four phases of a typical development cycle, successively replacing each other - crisis, depression, revival and recovery. An analysis

of the industrial cycle lasting 7-12 years allowed Marxists to identify the crisis in its typical forms - overproduction of goods, reduction in loans and an increase in loan interest. These processes lead to a drop in profits, a reduction and curtailment of production, an unrestrained increase in financial debts, bank failures and bankruptcies of enterprises in various sectors of the economy.

Economist N. Kondratyev, analyzing the emergence of large economic cycles, drew attention to the fact that before and at the beginning of an upward wave of each large cycle, serious changes are necessarily observed in the conditions of the economic life of society [6]. They are expressed in profound changes in technology, which, in turn, are preceded by outstanding technical discoveries and inventions, the involvement of new countries in world economic relations, changes in gold production and, as a consequence, in the rate of money circulation. The crisis arising from the accumulation of an excess of socio-economic, resource and raw materials, environmental, technological contradictions forces us to create solutions saving the situation, and the accumulated capital and high uncertainty of the investment environment allow such decisions to be translated into reality.

It is logical to conclude from this that any innovation occurs during a period of imbalance as a response of an ecosystem that, due to its elasticity, strives to return to an equilibrium state. That is why **only those innovations will be of the greatest value, which with the least expenditure of resources allow returning the lost state of economic equilibrium.**

The stability of an ecosystem is largely related to the stability and certainty of the distribution of roles and functions among its participants. Since resources are limited in the habitat, different species always compete for access to them. Known in ecology **the principle of competitive exclusion is expressed in the fact that in a habitat two species cannot occupy the same ecological niche.** In other words, different species cannot coexist in a community if they are fighting for the same livelihoods. In such a struggle, the species that makes the most efficient use of the resources it needs to survive will necessarily and certainly oust the less adapted representatives of the ecosystem.

The ecological response to this intrinsic biological challenge lies in the objectivity of **ecological niches** - independent sets of natural resources that are uniquely used by each individual species. This evolutionary solution allows many different species to coexist, which, having received a separate specialization, are integrated into the variegated biological picture of evolution.

Global managers argue that collaboration is emerging as a new form of leadership, and networks of trust must be built to survive in a highly competitive world. In nature, such mechanisms of mutual support are widespread and are known as symbiosis, when either both participants or only one participant receive benefits, while the other does not inconvenience and is indifferent to such cooperation. However, a third variant is also known, when the parasitic organism exists at the

expense of another, and this interaction gradually leads to the death of the donor organism.

4. Business ecosystem of innovative development of Kaluga region

The business ecosystem of Kaluga Region is represented by a wide network of organizations that determine how target companies (in our example, innovative companies) create and receive value (Figure 1).

Value for high-tech companies can come from capital (finance, infrastructure, intellectual property), human resources, partnerships, information, consulting, consumer interest, and customers.

The value chain is created through the coordinated activities of regional authorities, development institutions, clusters, business incubators, engineering centers, scientific, educational and consulting organizations, the media, etc. Participants can include both business platforms integrating resources and coordinating participants, as well as and independent logistics, financial, communication institutions, various advertising, marketing, consulting and educational organizations.

As an example, let us trace the chronology of building up the value chain by the development institutions of Kaluga Region (Table 1.)

As follows from the data in Table 1, in the developed business ecosystem of innovative development of Kaluga region, each participant has a unique set of resources and is able to develop their own specific competencies to create the total value of the ecosystem.

Following the typology of the development of business ecosystems proposed by J. F. Moore [7], it can be assumed that the community of development institutions has basically gone through the stages of origin, expansion and leadership, and now the ecosystem is changing, gradually forming a new evolutionary round (Table 2).

As noted above, the business ecosystem is subject to internal and external challenges that lead to the loss of the balance of the entire system. The interests of its participants are highly diversified and, as a result, sometimes conflict. In such a situation, the most effective and adequate solution may be those innovations that are aimed at improving coordination, motivation, involvement of new participants and strengthening the technological infrastructure.

5. Conclusion

The above comparative analysis of natural and economic ecosystems allows us to obtain a number of conclusions as well as to propose those directions for further development that should ensure the improvement of the ecosystem approach - an urgent and widely demanded method of modern economic science.

- At the heart of the emergence of a business ecosystem is a need or a problem, for the solution of which a

Figure 1. Business ecosystem of Kaluga region

Table 1. Stages of the formation of regional institutions that provide a value chain for the business development of innovation in Kaluga region

Year of foundation	Development Institute	Value provided by a development institution for an innovative company
2000	Regional Development Agency	Selection of sites and information support for investment activities
2007	Kaluga Region Development Corporation	Conclusion of agreements with an investor on the development of infrastructure in industrial parks (agreements on technological connection, investment agreements), transfer of rights to land plots within the boundaries of industrial parks to the investor, ensuring the supply of engineering and transport infrastructure to the boundaries of the land plot provided to the investor
2010	Agency for innovative development	Support of innovative companies participating in clusters, consulting on financing opportunities and promoting high-tech projects
2011	Center for Public-Private Partnership	Support for innovative projects implemented in the form of PPP
2018	Business Development Agency	Consulting on business and management issues, in particular, obtaining initial permits, government support measures, fundraising. "One-stop shop" for entrepreneurs in Kaluga region

chain of institutions and services is gradually formed. The ecosystem in its development in order to maintain sustainability creates innovations that can be aimed at

expanding the network of ecosystem participants, significant changes in the organization of the business model and management of the entire ecosystem. For example,

Table 2. Stages of increasing the value of the ecosystem of development institutions in Kaluga Region

#	Stage	Building on the value of the ecosystem
I	Birth	Creating a new value proposition for innovative companies. Formalization of the roles of institutions within the business ecosystem. Development of channels of interaction with organizations in the region.
II	Expansion	Building up the base of innovative companies to which institutions provide services. Improving the quality of services and their standardization.
III	Leadership	Formation of a common vision for further joint development. Providing complex services to innovative companies jointly by several institutions.
IV	Self-renewal	Restructuring the business ecosystem through the creation of innovation (for example, the involvement of new participants in the ecosystem, technological or organizational and managerial innovations) in order to preserve the sustainability of the ecosystem in the face of threats from emerging alternative ecosystems.

the necessary response to an increasing environmental threat is the coordination of changes in the economic ecosystem with the peculiarities of the development of the natural environment, and the value of the innovation and the potential of its use are reasonably determined from the point of view of its possible impact on the stability of the biological ecosystem.

- Management of the economic components of ecosystems, including legislative acts, methodologies and other knowledge, should be based on a developed and tested scientific base, including economic and environmental laws, as well as the results and conclusions of the general organizational science - tectology.
- Capital has no geographic boundaries and represents a kind of energy flow that flows fairly freely from one ecosystem participant to another due to the global nature of economic relations. Therefore, the ecosystem nature of the economy cannot be thought and initiated in isolation, in isolation from global trends and exclusively on the regional landscape or the level of individual states.
- Efficiency of an ecosystem is determined by sustainable development, which is based on maintaining the homogeneity of all elements in order to counteract the negative effects of the law of least. The creation and maintenance of a variety of forms of its participants can be taken as the main strategy for the development of an ecosystem, since the actual stability of any ecosystem is ensured by the preservation of species diversity.
- Possible measures to manage the growing environmental, institutional and demographic risks on the part of the participants in the regional business ecosystem of Kaluga region may be the involvement of new participants, including within the framework of cooperation

with other regions, the creation of a digital technological platform to improve the quality of decisions made, modernization of the organizational and functional structures of key development institutions.

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